
Protective Effect of Mesenchymal Stem Cells on Methotrexate-Induced Acute Toxicity on Liver of Adult Albino Rats

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Abstract: Our study aims at studying acute toxic effects of Methotrexate (MTX) on the liver of adult male albino rats and assessing the protective effect of Mesenchymal Stem Cells (MSCs) on the MTX-induced hepatotoxicity. Twenty-four adult male albino rats were divided into four groups, each of six. Rats in group I served as a negative control. Rats in group II received a single intraperitoneal injection of MTX at a dose of 10 mg/kg. Rats in groups III received MSCs therapy at a single intraperitoneal dose of 1×10^6 cells per rat. Rats in group IV received MSCs therapy at a single intraperitoneal dose of 2×10^6 cells per rat. Groups III and IV received MTX injection, same dose as group II. All animals were sacrificed on the 10th day. The liver was retained for histopathological and immunohistochemical examination. The sera were used for biochemical analysis. We demonstrated that MTX significantly increased serum concentrations of liver enzymes, reduced the serum antioxidant catalase enzymes levels, significantly increased serum Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentrations. In addition, it increased iNOS expression and caused prominent histological alterations in the liver. On the other hand, treatment MSCs was effective in significantly improving the liver enzymes, ameliorating the elevations of MDA, increasing catalase enzyme levels and decreasing the hepatic nitrosative stress, and ameliorating the pathological hepatic changes induced by MTX. We concluded that MSCs in both doses (one and two million cells/rat) could

ameliorate the hepatotoxicity induced by MTX. Applying such conclusion might have a great impact in future clinical practices.

Keywords: Mesenchymal Stem Cells, Methotrexate, Hepatotoxicity, Oxidative stress.

Introduction

Methotrexate (MTX) is a folic acid antagonist (Türkcü *et al.*, 2015). It has been widely used as an effective chemotherapeutic drug. In addition, it is a well-established treatment for different types of rheumatic diseases, autoimmune and inflammatory diseases (Abdel-Daim *et al.*, 2017; Rjiba-Touati *et al.*, 2017). Acute MTX toxicity is most commonly caused by an accidental overdose of MTX tablets by the patient or physician's prescription error (Madke and Singh, 2015).

Interaction of several factors including the patient's risk factors, type of disease, dosing schedule, and treatment duration, as well as the presence of genetic apoptotic factors can produce Methotrexate-induced cytotoxicity (Abdel-Daim *et al.*, 2017). Unfortunately, different vital organs are adversely affected especially the kidney and liver leading to limitation of the clinical usage of such drug (El-Sheikh *et al.*, 2015).

Several studies have suggested the role of oxidative stress as a mechanism underlying MTX toxicity (Tousson *et al.*, 2014). MTX targets nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH), part of the antioxidant defense system, by reducing its production, in addition, reactive oxygen species (ROS) are increased thus inducing oxidative stress and tissue damage (Yuksel *et al.*, 2017).

Up to 90% of MTX is cleared by the kidneys, and renal impairment; presented as acute kidney injury (AKI), which is attributed to tubular obstruction, due to the precipitation of MTX and its metabolites in the renal tubules (Severin *et al.*, 2016), in addition to the oxidative damage disturbing the balance of oxidant-antioxidant status (Yuksel *et al.*, 2017), can result in impairing its own elimination and increasing its systemic toxicity (Abdel-Daim *et al.*, 2017). The elevated toxic levels of MTX then contribute to multiple vital organ damage, including the liver (El-Sheikh *et al.*, 2015; Severin *et al.*, 2016).

Previous reports have demonstrated the pivotal role of oxidative stress in MTX hepatotoxicity. Excessive generation of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS/RNS), along with reduced antioxidant defense mechanism promote the development and progression of hepatotoxicity (Abo-Haded *et al.*, 2017). Recent studies have shown the possible role of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) in mediating MTX-induced hepatotoxicity (Hafez *et al.*, 2015).

Different anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-proliferative and immunomodulatory drugs have been used to decrease the toxic effects of MTX. However, none have provided complete protection against MTX toxicity. Thus, there is a wide field for new agents that can be used to prevent MTX-related damage on normal tissues (Türkcü *et al.*, 2015). There is an urgent need to develop an efficient protective therapy against drug-induced hepatotoxicity.

Therefore, we aimed at studying the acute toxic effects of MTX on the liver of adult male albino rats and assessing the protective effect of Mesenchymal Stem Cells on the MXT-induced hepatotoxicity.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the animal house, Physiology department, Faculty of Medicine, Suez Canal University, Egypt.

Rats

Twenty-four adult male wistar albino rats, weighing 150-250 g were obtained from the Egyptian Organization for Biological Products and Vaccines. All rats were kept for ten days at the experiment site for acclimatization. All rats were kept under optimal environmental conditions (12-hour light-dark cycles, temperature [$20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$] with moderate humidity [$60 \pm 5\%$] and adequate ventilation. Environmental conditions were standardized for all animal groups. They were housed in plastic cages maintained under standard pathogen-free conditions, in a quite non-stressful special room. They were freely fed on a standard pellet chow diet and tap water in clean containers. Necropsy was performed soon after an animal was sacrificed or found dead in a humane manner.

Isolation and characterization of Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs)

Two Rats were sacrificed by cervical dislocation and the tibia and femur were dissected. Medullary cavities of the bone were flushed with 10 ml of PBS for collection of marrow cells. The cells were centrifuged at 200 g for 10 minutes and the supernatant removed by aspiration. The cells were re-suspended in DMEM supplemented with 15% FBS, 100 U/ml Penicillin/Streptomycin and 50 U/ml Gentamicin and cultured at 37°C with 5% CO_2 . Adherent cells were harvested when reached 50-60% confluence with 0.25% trypsin.

Experimental Design

The rats were divided into four groups, each of six. Rats in group I served as a negative control, receiving saline only during the entire experimental period. Rats in group II received a single intraperitoneal injection of MTX (*MTX injection (50 mg) vial was purchased as an over-the-counter drug, manufactured by Shanxi*

PUDE Pharmaceutical Company, Ltd, Imported by Techno Pharma.) at a dose of 10 mg/kg bw (mimicking the acute exposure to an acute large dose in humans (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2013). The intraperitoneal LD50 of methotrexate is 6-25 mg/kg for rat (*Datasheet for MTX-New Zealand*).

Rats in groups III received MSCs therapy at a single intraperitoneal dose of 1×10^6 cells per rat. Rats in group IV received MSCs therapy at a single intraperitoneal dose of 2×10^6 cells per rat. On the same day of the experiment, rats in groups III and IV received I.P MTX injection, at the same dose used in group II rats. Animals were assigned to the groups in a simple random manner. All animals were sacrificed on the 10th day after blood sample collection via retro orbital plexus of veins.

The liver for all rats were fixed with 10% formalin for histo-pathological and immunohistochemical examination. The obtained blood samples were allowed to clot for 30 minutes then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes in order to obtain clear sera. The sera were then stored at -80°C for biochemical analysis (Liver functions tests and Oxidative stress markers).

Serum Biochemical Analysis

All assays were determined by using UV/VIS Spectrophotometer (Unico S2100 Series, USA) following manufacturer's protocol.

Liver functions tests

The assay kits used to analyze Albumin, Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) were purchased from (Spinreact, Spain). Serum albumin was measured according to method of (Rodkey, 1965). Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), also called serum Glutamate pyruvate transaminase (SGPT), was determined by colorimetric kinetic according to (Murray, 1984a) method. Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), also called serum Glutamate oxalacetate transaminase (SGOT), was determined by colorimetric kinetic according to (Murray, 1984b) method.

Oxidative stress markers

The oxidative stress Kits were purchased from (Biodiagnostics, Cairo, Egypt).

A) Malondialdehyde (MDA) or Lipid peroxide level: Thiobarbituric acid (TBA) reacts with lipid peroxide in acidic PH at temperature of 95°C for 30 min to form thiobarbituric acid reactive product, the absorbance of the resultant pink product can be measured at 534 nm as described by (Yagi, 1982).

B) Catalase: It is an antioxidant enzyme that is present in most aerobic cells containing a cytochrome system. It is considered as one of the body's defense

systems against Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), a strong oxidant that can cause intracellular damage. It was determined as described by (Aebi, 1984).

Histopathological and Immunohistochemical Examination

The specimens from the liver were collected and fixed in 10% formalin solution and embedded in paraffin. Five μm thick paraffin sections were prepared and then routinely stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) dyes. Stained slides were microscopically analyzed using light microscopy (Olympus CX41). Necroinflammatory score (grade) and fibrosis stage of liver slides evaluated according to ISHAK score (Westin *et al.*, 1999).

For immunohistochemical staining, sections were fixed at 65° C for 1 h. Trilogy pretreatment (deparaffinization, rehydration, and antigen unmasking) was used to enhance standardization of the pretreatment step and produce results that are more consistent. The rabbit polyclonal antibody against inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), was employed as it is (ready to use) according to their manufacturer's specification.

After applying the antibodies, slides were incubated overnight at 4°C followed by 20 min of Poly HRP enzyme conjugation. Afterwards, DAB chromogen was applied for 2 min and then rinsed, followed by counterstaining with Mayer hematoxylin before examination under the light microscope.

Statistical analysis

Collected data throughout laboratory techniques and outcome measures were coded, entered and analyzed using the based statistics program: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 20.0.

The variables were expressed in the form of means and standard deviation.

ANOVA test was used to determine any significance differences between the mean levels of continuous variables (control and experimental groups). Differences were considered significant at $P < 0.01$.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Statement on the welfare of animals: All Faculty of Medicine, Suez Canal University, Egypt guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed. All procedures performed in the study involving animals were in accordance with the ethical standards of the Research Ethics Committee (REC) at Faculty of Medicine, Suez Canal University, Egypt at which the study was conducted. (Permit number 3681).

Results

Biochemical Findings

Hepatic functional serum marker concentrations

Intraperitoneal injection of MTX significantly increased serum concentrations of ALT, AST enzymes, compared to normal control levels ($p < 0.01$). However there were no observed significant effects on albumin levels. Upon treatment of MTX-injected rats with MSCs (at one million and two million cells/rat) significantly reduced the elevation of ALT levels by 55.4% and 70.3%, AST levels by 30.93% and 33.5% respectively.

Treatment of MTX-injected rat with both doses of MSCs restored serum concentrations of these parameters to normal control levels. However, treatment of MTX-injected rats with two million stem cells/rat was more effective in reducing the elevated serum levels of ALT and AST than treatment with one million stem cells/rat (**Table 1**).

Serum Antioxidant Activity

MTX-injected rats showed a marked reduction in the serum antioxidant catalase enzymes levels, as well as significant increase in serum MDA concentrations ($p < 0.01$). Administration of MSCs (at one million and two million cells/rat) significantly ameliorated the elevations of MDA concentrations in MTX-injected rat ($p < 0.01$). Moreover, this increased activities of CAT enzyme. However, treatment of MTX-injected rats with two million stem cells/rat was more effective than treatment with one million stem cells/rat (**Table 2**).

Histopathological and Immunohistochemical findings

Histopathological examination of Liver

Histopathological examination of liver showed normal structure in all groups (control, MTX, MTX-treated with MSCs) as regards to the lobular architecture, central vein, and radiating hepatic cords (**Figures 1a, 2a, 3a respectively**).

For the MTX group, the liver showed marked dilatation and congestion of portal vein/ sinusoids and central veins, portal area showed moderate inflammatory cells infiltrate in some portal areas (point 2), No Periportal or periseptal interface hepatitis (piecemeal necrosis) (point 0), No confluent necrosis (point 0), Five to ten foci per 10 objective of Focal (spotty) lytic necrosis, apoptosis and focal inflammation (point 3) (**Ishak grade "Necroinflammatory score"= 5/8**), bile duct hyperplasia, Fibrous expansion of some portal areas, without short fibrous septa (**Ishak stage 1/6**) (**Figure 2a**).

On the contrary, with MSCs therapy (two million cells/rat), liver showed mild dilatation and congestion of portal vein, kupffer cells hyperplasia, portal area showed mild inflammatory cells infiltrate in some portal areas (point 1), No Periportal or periseptal interface hepatitis (piecemeal necrosis) (point 0), No confluent necrosis (point 0), Two to four foci per 10 objective of focal (spotty) lytic necrosis, apoptosis and focal inflammation (point 2). (**Ishak grade “Necroinflammatory score”= 3/8**), bile duct hyperplasia, no fibrosis (**Ishak stage=0/6**) (**Figure 3a**).

Effects of MTX and MSCs therapy in MTX-injected rats on Hepatic iNOS Expression

Immunohistochemical staining of rat liver sections with iNOS was performed to confirm nitrosative stress. Immunohistochemical staining of control rat liver with iNOS revealed scattered cytoplasmic expression of iNOS in the portal and sinusoidal vascular endothelia, and kupffer cells in between lobular architectures (**Figure 1b**). As regards to iNOS expression in MTX group, there is relative increase in iNOS expression, compared to both MSCs therapy and control groups, in the form of positive cytoplasmic brownish stain for iNOS in kupffer cells scattered in between hepatocyte lobules/ lymphocyte infiltrate in hepatic lobules and portal area (**Figures 1b, 2b and 3b**).

Table 1. Ameliorative effects of mesenchymal stem cells on serum concentrations of renal and hepatic injury markers in adult male wistar albino rats exposed to methotrexate

Group	ALT	AST	Serum Albumin
Control	42.75 ± 1.50	77.25 ± 30.23	3.30 ± 0.35
MTX (10 mg/Kg)	139.80 ± 48.87 [‡]	137.20 ± 13.22 [‡]	3.33 ± 0.40
MTX (10 mg/kg) + one million stem cells	62.40 ± 35.42 [*]	94.75 ± 14.27 [*]	3.88 ± 0.05
MTX (10 mg/kg) + two millions stem cells	41.50 ± 4.93 [*]	91.25 ± 7.50 [*]	3.50 ± 0.32

Values are means ±SD.
[‡] Significant change at p < 0.01 with respect to the negative control group.
^{*} Significant change at p < 0.01 with respect to the MTX group as the positive control group.
 ALT: Alanine aminotransferase; AST: Aspartate aminotransferase or transaminase

Table 2. Ameliorative effects of mesenchymal stem cells on serum concentrations of lipid peroxidation and antioxidant markers in adult male wistar albino rats exposed to methotrexate

Group	Malonaldehyde	Catalase
Control	42.57±33.47	948.10±46.66
MTX (10 mg/Kg)	116.61±36.11 [‡]	557.73±188.50 [‡]
MTX (10 mg/kg) + one million stem cells	69.74±27.08 *	773.62±45.03 *
MTX (10 mg/kg) + two millions stem cells	46.21±35.2 *	820.40±171.04 *

Values are means ±SD.
[‡] Significant change at $p < 0.01$ with respect to the negative control group.
*Significant change at $p < 0.01$ with respect to the MTX group as the positive control group.

Figure 1a. Normal liver tissue in control group showed preserved lobular arrangement of hepatocytes, intervening sinusoids, Kupffer cells in between, portal area with portal vein, normal hepatic artery and bile duct in portal area. No inflammation or degenerative/reactive changes (H&E X200).

Figure 1b. In control group, scattered faint positive cytoplasmic brownish stain for iNOs in kupffer cells scattered in between hepatocyte lobules and portal and sinusoidal vascular endothelia (arrows) (IHC x 200).

Figure 2a. Liver tissue for MTX group showed preserved lobules of hepatocytes, severe congestion of sinusoids, pronounced lymphocytic infiltrate of hepatocytes lobules and kupffer cells hyperplasia, No Fibrosis (H&E x 200)

Figure 2b. For MTX group, strong positive cytoplasmic brownish stain for iNOs in kupffer cells in between hepatocyte lobules/ lymphocyte infiltrate in hepatic lobules and portal area (IHC x 200)

Figure 3a. Liver tissue in MTX group treated with Mesenchymal stem cells (two million cells/rat) showed preserved lobules of hepatocytes, mild congestion of portal vein, sinusoids (black arrow). Focal lytic necrosis of hepatocytes (green arrow) and kupffer cells hyperplasia (arrow head), portal area showed mild inflammatory cells infiltrate (green arrow), bile duct hyperplasia (double headed arrow), no fibrosis (H&E x 200).

Figure 3a.1. Liver tissue in MTX group treated with Mesenchymal stem cells (two million cells/rat) showed preserved lobules of hepatocytes, mild congestion of sinusoids (black arrow), Kupffer cells hyperplasia (green arrow), focal pyknotic nuclei (lytic necrosis) of hepatocytes (white circle) (H&E x 400).

Figure 3b. In MTX group treated with Mesenchymal stem cells (two million cells/rat), positive cytoplasmic brownish stain for iNOs in Kupffer cells scattered in between hepatocyte lobules/lymphocyte infiltrate in hepatic lobules and portal area (IHC x 200).

Discussion

Methotrexate (MTX), despite being a widely used chemotherapeutic and immunosuppressive agent, it has many side effects especially being hepatotoxic. This study addressed the potential protective effect of bone marrow derived MSCs on MTX liver acute toxicity. Role of MSCs in treatment of MTX-induced toxicity is not clear enough to be used in clinical trials. Accordingly, our experimental study may have a great potential to denote that the MSCs could be able to significantly reduce the biochemical and histological alterations, induced by MTX.

As regards to the MTX-induced hepatotoxicity, the mechanisms are still unclear. However, this could be attributed to its cellular pathway. Methotrexate indirectly affects MTHFR (methylene-tetrahydro folate reductase) and hence the generation of methionine from homocysteine (Pandit *et al.*, 2012). Kumari (2016) stated that the increased homocysteine levels increase production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as MDA. Altered balance between ROS production and antioxidant defenses leads to a state of “oxidative stress”, which leads to various pathological conditions in different organs all over the body (Kumari, 2016). In addition, increased ROS can lead to several structural and functional abnormalities due to the damage they cause to lipids, proteins, and nucleic acids of all cells of the body (Sönmez *et al.*, 2012).

The state of methotrexate induced oxidative stress was evidenced in our study by the significant increase in serum MDA level; an oxidant marker and indicator of tissue lipid peroxidation, caused by ROS, suggesting that lipid peroxidation is an important contributing factor to the MTX-induced tissue damage (Şener *et al.*, 2006), associated with significant decrease of serum catalase; an antioxidant enzyme that converts the potentially harmful hydrogen peroxide into oxygen and water (Weydert and Cullen, 2010), in MTX-induced toxicity rats, when compared with control rats.

The reduction in the level of antioxidant defense system may be attributed to a significant reduction in Glutathione (GSH) level, an important antioxidant protecting against ROS, induced by MTX. This in turn may be explained by the reduction of cellular NADPH pool; important for maintenance of the reduced form of cellular GSH by action of glutathione reductase.

This reduction of the NADPH may be related to the inhibition of the cytosolic nicotinamide adenosine diphosphate (NADP)-dependent dehydrogenases and NADP malic enzymes (Caetano *et al.*, 1997; Babiak *et al.*, 1998; Jahovic *et al.*, 2003; Çakır *et al.*, 2011; Abdel-Raheem and Khedr, 2014; Pınar *et al.*, 2018).

In addition, MTX induces the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines as COX-2, TNF- α , iNOS, MMP 9, interleukin IL-1 β and IL-6 as a result of up-regulation of the expression of nuclear factor-kappaB (NF- κ B). This leads to tissue damage, apoptosis and endothelial dysfunction (Yamamoto and Gaynor, 2004; El-Gowilly *et al.*, 2015; Natarajan *et al.*, 2018). Methotrexate induced oxidative stress creates a nitrosative inflammatory state in hepatic tissue. El-Sheikh *et al.*, (2015) stated that MTX causes increased hepatic nitric oxide, with upregulation of inducible nitric oxide synthase (El-Sheikh *et al.*, 2015), which is proved by the increased cytoplasmic expression of iNOS in hepatic tissue (>50%) in our MTX-induced toxicity rats compared to scattered cytoplasmic iNOS expression (<10%) in normal rats. This result suggested that the peroxidation reaction was higher in MTX group than control group.

Moreover, the MTX induced nitrosative stress leads to marked inflammation in liver tissue. In agreement with El-Sheikh *et al.*, (2015), MTX toxicity induced marked inflammation of the hepatic tissue, associated with significant increase of serum transaminases (ALT & AST) compared with control group. There were prominent pathological changes in the liver tissue of MTX group including congestion of portal vein/ sinusoids and central veins, inflammatory cells infiltrate in some portal areas, Focal (spotty) lytic necrosis, apoptosis and focal inflammation, bile duct hyperplasia, Fibrous expansion of some portal areas, without short fibrous septa observed compared to control group. The Ishak score of liver tissue revealed inflammatory and fibrosis score of (5/8, 1/6 respectively) in MTX group. We observed that the histopathological changes of the liver tissues were concomitant with the disturbance in the balance of oxidant–antioxidant status and the increased hepatic iNOS expression.

Ayatollahi *et al.*, (2014) demonstrated that MSCs transplantation has an anti-oxidant protective effect against oxidative stress induced liver injury. That is why, in current study, rats were treated with MSCs; used in two different doses (one and two millions MSCs), aiming to alleviate the methotrexate toxicity effects (Ayatollahi *et al.*, 2014). Our present study showed that transplantation of MSCs improved the imbalance of oxidant/antioxidant capacity, a significant reduction in serum MDA level as well as a significant elevation of serum catalase level in group III and IV (MTX-induced toxicity group treated with MSCs) as compared to group II (MTX-induced toxicity with no treatment). As a sequelae, the restoration of oxidant/antioxidant balance, resulted in decreasing the hepatic nitrosative stress, which was evidenced by marked decrease in iNOS expression in liver tissue (10- <50%) compared to the increased cytoplasmic expression of iNOS in liver tissue (>50%) in MTX-induced toxicity group with no MSCs transplantation.

Moreover, interestingly, MSCs ameliorated the histological alteration in hepatocytes induced by MTX. Supporting to our result, Gazdic *et al.*, (2018), found that MSCs protect from acute liver injury. Moreover, In agreement with Ayatollahi *et al.*, (2014) histopathological assessment of hepatic tissue showed significant improvement of Ishak inflammatory and fibrosis score from (5/8, 1/6 respectively) in MTX-induced toxicity group, to (3/8, 0/6 respectively) in MSCs treated group (in either dose).

The MSCs induced improvement in MTX toxicity was not only structural, but it was also functional. MSCs transplantation (in either dose) caused significant improvement of serum transaminases (ALT & AST) level compared to the levels for MTX-induced toxicity group.

Conclusion

We concluded that MSCs in both doses (one and two million cells/rat) could ameliorate the hepatotoxicity induced by MTX. Applying such conclusion might have a great impact in preventing the MTX-induced hepatotoxicity during MTX therapy strategies.

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